

RUPTURE OF 7075/AL₂O₃ COMPOSITES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: Aluminum alloy matrix composites 7075 with 10 and 15% Al₂O₃ particles have been deformed by torsion in the range 250-540°C at strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.1-4 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The strength decreased gradually as test temperature rose and $\dot{\epsilon}$ declined; but maximum ductility was found at 400°C. Optical and scanning electron microscopic examination showed that particles became aligned at an angle near 45° to the torsion axis and did not break up. Cracked particles were sometimes observed in the shoulder and more often in the gage. All specimens tested at 300-500°C had the cracks on the surface; these were rows of short cracks propagated in the plane of maximum shear stress. At 400°C in both composites with 10 and 15% Al₂O₃, samples contained many cracks on the surface and a few big cracks inside the gage; particles were the sites for formation of fine cracks. At 500°C, polarized optical microscopy revealed mainly elongated grains with internal substructure and also some areas of fine equiaxed crystallites. The drop in ductility at 500°C has been related to the formation of large precipitate particles at that temperature.

KEYWORDS: particulate, aluminum matrix, hot workability, rupture, cracking, TEM, SEM, optical microscopy, subgrains, grain boundary precipitates

INTRODUCTION

Particulate Al matrix composites (AMC) synthesized by liquid metal mixing have great potential because of their improved mechanical properties, low density and reasonable cost. Components may be finally produced by casting directly to shape or to billets for subsequent mechanical shaping, such as extrusion [1-6]. While this last type of processing has the possibility of rapid, large volume production, it requires that the AMC have adequate workability which is always reduced relative to the matrix alloy by the reinforcing particles.

The aluminum matrix composites derive their mechanical properties from the high dislocation density and the residual stresses induced by the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (ΔCTE) [2,6-9]. The strengthening can be increased by fine substructures or grain sizes developed by TMP which are also designed to produce the required shape. The induced dislocation densities increase with rising strain and strain rate and falling temperature to an even greater extent than in the matrix alloy as the particle volume fraction increases because of the preexisting ΔCTE dislocations and the enhancement of inhomogeneous plastic flow by the rigid particles [5,6-29]. The properties developed depend strongly on the alloy in which the solutes, dispersoids and precipitates also influence the TMP results [22,26-32]. Finally the strength of the matrix may be augmented in some alloys by precipitation hardening which is frequently altered compared to the bulk alloys by the presence of the high dislocation

densities and residual stresses. Matrix alloys are generally strengthened by the precipitates to a greater degree in the order 6000 series (Mg_2Si), 2000 series ($CuAl_2$) and 7000 series ($Zn-Cu-Mg$) [27-31,33-39].

Figure 1. Schematic torsion flow curves of 7075/15%Al₂O₃ (a) showing the development a long steady state plateau at 400°C. The 6061 and A356 composites with 15%SiC exhibit much lower flow stresses and extensive plateaus at 500°C, 1 s⁻¹. (b) The ductility of 7075/15%Al₂O₃ increases as strain rate decreases most noticeably near the temperature of the maximum. The ductility of 7075/10%Al₂O₃ is higher near the maximum due to the lower particle content but is not different at 500 and 540°C.

The workability at high temperatures of the composites depends strongly on the presence of the reinforcing particles. The matrix up to about 30% by volume contains subgrains produced by dynamic recovery DRV; however, these are always smaller, less polygonized and more misoriented than in the alloy alone under the same conditions [14-22,26-31,38,39]. In another 30%, there are dense dislocation tangles with limited cellularity, either close to the particles or in shear bands defined by groups of particles. In the remaining regions, there are cellular structures with high misorientation walls (possibly derived from the second regions as a result of DRV or dynamic recrystallization DRX) [13,15-22,26-31]. The microstructure tends to move towards the second type from an increase in particle volume fraction or a decrease in temperature, whereas the partial DRX regions are favored by increase in both these factors. Neither the high density of dislocations nor the DRX structures are found in the matrix alloys during hot working [33,34,40]. Moreover, the DRX regions are quite different from classical DRX [40,41] in that growth of the grains associated with mobile high angle boundaries does not occur so that there is no spread of recrystallization throughout the matrix [27-29].

The workability depends greatly on the matrix since the more highly alloyed (increasing in order 6000, 2000 and 7000 series) are generally stronger due to solute or particles which have various sizes and distributions dependent in previous history [26-28,33-37]. In general higher matrix strength reduces the ductility because of higher stress concentrations which cause particle matrix decohesion much more frequently than particle fracture as at ambient temperature [1,11,13,23-25]. In consequence, the ductility increases as the temperature rises

reaching true fracture strains of ϵ_f about 2 at 400°C, 1 s⁻¹ in torsion, which is indicative of reasonable workability for extrusion or rolling [8-11,16,25]. The ductility also depends on specific features of the matrix for example in A356 (7% Si) alloy or matrix the size and distribution of the 6.5% Si eutectic particles has a deleterious effect unless greatly refined by strontium modification as described previously [25,26]. While composites with alloys A356, 6061 and 2618 increase in ductility as T rises above 400°C [9,10,22,25,26], the ductility of 7075 composites decreases markedly between 400 and 500°C [30-32]. The objective is to examine the failures in 7075/10%Al₂O₃ and 7075/15%Al₂O₃ in order to clarify the causes.

Figure 2. Optical micrographs exhibiting: (a) at 250°C, 1 s⁻¹ (unpolished), cellular particle distribution and large crack possibly at a shrinkage defect; (b) 500°C, 1 s⁻¹ (anodized, polarized light) elongated grains and small crystallites difficult to distinguish from particles.

TECHNIQUES

The torsion tests are conducted at constant temperature T (200-540°C) and surface strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ (0.01-4 s⁻¹), to determine the surface stress σ (von Mises uniaxial equivalent) according to techniques and principles explained frequently before [9,10,32,41]. The flow curves strain harden to a peak stress σ_p and then decline rapidly to failure at 200 or 300° but at 400 and 500°C decline very gradually to a fracture strain ϵ_f , which may be the result of deformation heating, microstructural evolution or gradual formation of voids. Constitutive equations of the sinh-Arrhenius type relating σ_{max} to T and $\dot{\epsilon}$ have been derived for use in finite element modeling of extrusion [9,10,32,42]. After fracture, the non-rotating end is extracted by longitudinally displacing the load cell mount to permit rapid quenching in less than 3 s.

The specimens are examined on a tangential flat (normal to radius just below the gage surface) by either optical microscopy (OM) of unetched surfaces or of anodized surfaces with polarization (POM) [28]. The same tangential section was used for SEM examination. For TEM, slices were cut normal to a radius and near the surface; they were thinned by mechanical dimpling and ion milling on a GATAN ion mill [17-20,30].

In torsion, initially equiaxed grains near the specimen surface are elongated and twisted into helicoids (like spiral springs) about the torsion axis to a degree dependent on the total strain [41]. The specimen surface becomes rumpled in association with these spirals and the uniformity of deformation can be assessed by macroscopic examination. The tangential

section exhibits the elongated and thinned grains at an angle to the torsion axis which increases as strain rises; a second phase becomes strung out along the grain boundaries. The tangential flat is usually produced in unison with a chord section in the attached shoulder so it is possible to observe the original structure and the increase in strain across the transition file. In contrast to optical microscopy, SEM permits observation of both the polished section and the adjacent surface at high magnification as a result of the great depth of focus. With an ability to peer into them, shallow surface cracks may be tracked from the curved surface into the flat tangential section where they terminate because they have been polished away. The depth of cracks entering from the surface was clearly confirmed on longitudinal diametral sections.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of tangential section of 7075/10%Al₂O₃ at 300°C, 0.1 s⁻¹: (a) one of the few large cracks away from the rupture zone very close to the surface. Particles are associated with it but there is evidence of the matrix tearing. Note the bifurcation where the crack meets a large particle and the decohesion ahead of it; (b) some cracked Al₂O₃ particles with almost no evidence of decohesion.

RESULTS

Some schematic flow curves with representative flow stresses are shown for 7075/15%Al₂O₃ and 7075/10%Al₂O₃ along with 6061/15%SiC and A356/15% SiC for comparison (Fig. 1) [9,10,21,25,26,32]. The flow stress is clearly reduced by increase in T and decrease in $\dot{\epsilon}$. The 7075 composites are stronger than the others notably at low T and the strength is raised by the higher volume fraction of reinforcements. All the curves exhibit long slightly drooping plateaus at 400°C compared to limited ductility at 300°C. On raising T to 500°C, the plateaus are much curtailed for 7075 composites but extended for 6061 and A356 ones. In Fig. 2, the fracture strains ϵ_f , rise rapidly with rising T near 250-350°C and passes through a maximum at 400°C for 7075 whereas it continues to increase at a slower rate for the other two matrices [9,10,22,25-28,32].

The optical micrographs of unpolished sections exhibit the reinforcing particles in a fairly uniform array, however, they are sometimes in cells and occasionally agglomerated as a result of their exclusion by the fast growing primary dendrites (Fig. 2a) [1,2,6,16-21,31]. In some specimens with high strains, the particles are lined up parallel to the spiral grain boundaries.

In longitudinal sections showing their depth, the cracks run irregularly through the matrix, including many particles as though they had connected voids at interfaces. There are occasions when the cracks are quite wide and in contact with clusters of particles indicative of shrinkage voids from solidification (Fig 2a).

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of tangent section, surface of 7075/10%Al₂O₃ at 400°C, 0.1 s⁻¹: (a) many medium sized surface cracks with some extending into the section; (b) deepest end of the largest crack showing interaction with closely spaced particles; and (c) at higher strain rate 4 s⁻¹, a deep narrow crack associated with several particles, none are broken.

The SEM examination of the 7075/10%Al₂O₃ composite on the tangential section (after repeated polishings to improve the quality) revealed cracking variation with T and $\dot{\epsilon}$. At 300°C 0.1 s⁻¹ ($\epsilon_f = 1.80$) in regions away from the principal one, many short narrow cracks were barely visible. In the areas scanned (Fig. 3), one large crack was noted at the boundary of the polished tangent and the surface; it was comparatively wide and was associated with some particles. Sharper secondary cracks emanated from the tip (near a particle) and one of these ran along a reinforcement interface. Many particles appeared to be cracked, although the pieces had not been separated by plastic strain; however, some particles in the shoulder chord section nearby were also cracked. Secondary cracks and fissures between more closely spaced particles were observed near the principal fracture.

At 400°C 0.1 s⁻¹ ($\epsilon_f = 2.3$, the maximum), many cracks were apparent along the gage surface, all lying roughly parallel to the plane of maximum shear stress; however they did contain sharp kinks and bifurcations associated with particles (Fig. 4). There were a few cracks in the tangential section mostly at the edge where it meets the surface. One such crack which obviously had penetrated downwards from the surface is quite wide in the axial direction and is very irregular possibly indicating a solidification defect. Near the fracture surface there were many auxiliary cracks in which one could see protruding particles as well as tears at many particles. The matrix fracture appears dimpled, that is ductile; this would be consistent with observations of 25°C fractures [23,24]. At 400°C, 4 s⁻¹ ($\epsilon_f = 1.1$), the behaviour was similar to the previous specimen; however the surface cracks were shorter and not so open. The cracking directions seemed to be primarily defined by the deformation geometry and to

touch randomly on particles where were not broken. However 40-50% of the particles were broken at 4 s^{-1} compared to only a few at 0.1 s^{-1} (some broken in the shoulder).

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of 7075/10%Al₂O₃ near tangent-surface intersection for 500°C, 0.1 s⁻¹: (a) several very large deep cracks; (b) away from the cracks mainly in the matrix, particles exhibit neither fracture nor decohesion.

At 500°C, 1 s⁻¹ ($\epsilon_f = 0.4$), there were many fewer cracks than at 400; 0.1 s⁻¹ but they were much larger, more opened up and penetrating more deeply into the tangential section (Fig. 5). While much of the crack was in the matrix, the end was associated with decohesion in a cluster of particles. Very few particles were broken; although some of the larger ones in the shoulder were cracked. In the 7075/15%Al₂O₃ composite under the same conditions ($\epsilon_f = 0.45$), few cracks were observed away from the main crack and the particles were not broken. There appeared to be voids at some particles preferentially at clusters, but most interfaces appeared perfect.

The examination of the tangential sections by POM (Fig. 2b) was partially successful only at the highest temperature because at lower T the cells were not well developed [31]. Moreover, the particles gave varying contrast due to their optical characteristics in contrast to their uniform dark appearance against the bright unetched matrix. In the specimens at 500°C (0.1 or 1 s⁻¹), some elongated grains showed uniform contrast due to the subgrains being at a similar angle to the extinction condition (Fig. 2b). Other grains close to polarizing extinction exhibited cells with a range of contrasts; however, the misorientations cannot be determined by this method. There appeared to be equiaxed recrystallized grains separating the long grains but more careful analysis revealed that most of these were particles [31]. In a specimen at 400°C, 0.1 s⁻¹, the TEM examinations revealed substructures of variable density, degree of polygonization and misorientation: subgrains away from Al₂O₃ particles and either fine cells or DRX grains near to them. (Fig. 6) [30]. In addition the precipitates occurring at different temperatures were identified and their association with subboundaries or grain boundaries noted (Fig. 7).

DISCUSSION

The ductility of the 7075 composites up to 400°C varies with T and $\dot{\epsilon}$ in a similar way to that of other AMC which were all much less than their respective matrices [9,10,25-28]; this indicates that the fracture is controlled by the matrix particle interactions. The drop in

ductility of 7075 composites in similarity to the matrix alloy and dissimilarity to other AMC indicates that this is likely a matrix feature. The matrix character has been shown to significantly affect ϵ_f in the case of A356 where fine Si eutectic particles in the composite give rise to a ductility equaling that of unmodified A356 alloy in which the Si particles look like $12\ \mu\text{m}$ long needles but are actually interconnected flakes [25,26]. The decrease in ductility of 7075 with such rise in T is well known and has been associated to large precipitates, when one might expect them to be dissolving [35-37].

Figure 6. Bright field images 7075/15% Al_2O_3 of subgrains after deformation at 400°C and $0.1\ \text{s}^{-1}$: a) large subgrains without Al_2O_3 particles; (b) small subgrains in the neighborhood of Al_2O_3 particles; (c) Nucleation of new grains at Al_2O_3 particles A. Note η precipitates nucleated on dispersoids of E phase ($\text{Al}_{18}\text{Cr}_2\text{Mg}_3$) at B.

The POM and TEM observations (Figs. 2b,6) provide evidence of substructures which are equivalent to those in other AMC [6,11,12,14,16-23]. The occurrence of subgrains agrees with other observations of 7075/ Al_2O_3 composites [38]. The increase in scale and cellularity of the substructure as T rises is consistent with the decline in flow stress which has been greater in 7075 composites than those of other matrices thus resulting in more closely similar high T values. The decrease in ductility is thus not due to especially high dislocation densities and associated stress concentrations.

The SEM observations show an alteration in the cracking behavior. At 300°C (Fig. 3), where the stress is high there is evidence of cracked particles, decohesion and a few random cracks because ϵ_f is rather low due to rapid fracture at the principal crack which appears related to linking up of voids at particle matrix interfaces. At 400°C (Fig. 4), the flow stress is decreased so there is reduced particle damage but there are many more minor cracks which have had opportunity to develop because of the much greater fracture strain. At 500° , (Fig. 5) there are no broken particles, much less decohesion and almost no minor cracks because of the low fracture strain indicative of matrix microstructural instabilities which enhance crack

propagation. Foils from different deformation temperatures show alteration of particle morphologies in TEM examination [37]. At 500°C, large precipitates are found mainly in grain boundaries (Fig. 7); diffraction shows that these are a phase which is absent at lower T because other metastable particles had formed with much smaller size and more uniform distribution.

Figure 7. Nonuniform precipitation of T phase inside of subgrains in grain boundaries and at triple junctions after deformation at 500°C and 1 s^{-1} . SAD patterns taken from individual T phase particles, $(\text{AlZn})_{49}\text{Mg}_{32}$ in (100), (112) and (110) matrix orientations.

The low ductilities of the 7075 composites above 450°C (Fig. 1), are thus seen to be a peculiarity of the matrix alloy in developing new stable precipitates mainly at grain boundaries [37]. The ductility could be improved by delaying the formation of this phase until the forming process is completed. Starting with material in the solution treated condition has the disadvantage that the high solute level and dynamic precipitation of fine particles at initiation of straining may cause very high stress peaks which would require extreme break-out pressures in extrusion [5,34,43,44]. The alternative is to lock the alloying elements in fairly large particles stabilized at a lower temperature so that it would require a prolonged time to redissolve them at the high temperature. This procedure would also lead to lower extrusion pressures. The presence of the deleterious T phase particles leads to poor surface quality in 7000 series extrusions thus conferring on these alloys reputation for very poor extrudability.

CONCLUSIONS

For the 7075 composites with 10 or 20% Al_2O_3 the flow stress declines from 200 to 540°C and the level of DRV with formation of subgrains rises in a manner similar to composites of 6061 and A356 alloys. The 7075 composite ductility rises like the others up to 400°C but in contrast decreases severely at 500 and 540°C in similarity to the bulk alloy behavior. Up to 400°C, cracks initiate at matrix-particle interfaces and propagate by linking up through the

matrix. At 500°C there is limited void formation but matrix failure at a low strain. The cause appears to be invigorated precipitation of a T phase as large particles on the grain boundaries

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